

**LA TRADUCTION DES BANDES-ANNONCES
COMME ACTE DE DISCOURS MULTIMODAL /
TRANSLATING FILM TRAILERS
AS AN ACT OF MULTIMODAL DISCOURSE**

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The movie trailer presents a specific form of audiovisual discourse with a persuasive function, built on a fragmentary and symbolic narrative structure. Beyond its informational and movie promotion dimension, it functions as a multimodal product composed of semiotic elements and verbal text that interact and complement each other. The translation of the trailer therefore becomes an act of discursive and cultural (re)construction. This paper proposes an exploration of trailer translation from an intersemiotic perspective, analyzing how audiovisual translation negotiates meaning in a condensed and dynamic communicative framework, drawing attention to how localization strategies succeed (or not) in balancing technical constraints, cultural requirements and target audience expectations.